

Militants and Militias: Authoritarian Legacies and the Political Economy of War in Sudan

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Introduction

The ongoing war in Sudan represents, first and foremost, one of the worst humanitarian crises in the world. In just over two years since it began in April 2023, the conflict has resulted in over 13 million displaced persons and approximately 3 million refugees. It has also witnessed a brutal pattern of ethnically targeted killings, sexual violence, and a wide range of atrocities against civilians. Like all wars, it is not, as some analysts have observed, a “nihilistic” war about “nothing” (Applebaum 2025), that is, one absent political, economic, and ideological foundation. Indeed, the war has demonstrated that Sudan is central to understanding some of the most urgent and important themes in the turbulent politics of the Middle East and North Africa. These include the relationship of authoritarianism and civil conflict; the structural and social inequalities underpinning popular mobilization and revolution; the political consequences of the erosion of state capacity in the context of increasingly informalized economies; the rise of para-military militias as key actors in competing attempts at state building; the politics of extraction and critical

minerals in the context of regional instability; and the complicated role of Islamism in domestic and regional politics.

Even prior to 2023, Sudan was one of the most conflict-affected countries in the Middle East and the Horn of Africa. It has long faced multiple challenges, including deep inequality, regional imbalances between center and periphery, subregional armed conflicts, unaccountable governance, and the dominance of the security and para-military militias over the political and economic spheres. In what now appears as a prelude to the war, on October 25, 2021, the country witnessed a military coup that stalled the transition to a civilian democracy, which began in the aftermath of the vibrant 2018 pro-democracy uprising that ousted President Omar al-Bashir. Following the 2021 coup, protests calling for a return to civilian rule continued throughout the country. These protests compelled the country’s military and paramilitary militias, in partnership at the time, to agree to negotiations with the civilian opposition to return the country to a path toward a transition to democracy. However, the negotiations, convened under the auspices of the UN, Saudi Arabia, and the

U.S., under what was termed the “framework agreement,” were woefully unsuccessful. The Sudan Armed Forces (SAF) and the militia led by Mohamed Hamdan Dagalo, known as the Rapid Support Forces (RSF), disagreed over merging the RSF into the regular national standing army, an army that has long been dominated by Islamist cadres appointed by the ousted Bashir regime.

This essay provides a deeper understanding of the root causes of the present war in Sudan by focusing on the legacy of authoritarianism and structural drivers of the war. In doing so, I focus on (1) the nature of the formal and illicit economy upon which the “deep state” was established under the former Islamist regime, (2) internal conflicts in the country reflecting long-standing, historical, social and political divisions, (3) the deeply entrenched military security and coercive parallel security and coercive apparatus, (4) external forces shaping the conflict, (5) and the “logic” of violence as an outcome of rival nascent state building in the context of war.

The Political Economy of War

At the heart of Sudan’s war are two interrelated levels of conflict dating from independence. The first is the power struggle within the Center between groups representing traditional and modern segments of Sudanese civil society. In general terms, conflict in the Center is between the military and groups in civil society linked to the traditional Sufi-led political parties (i.e., the Umma and Democratic Unionist Parties) and Arabized ethnic groups on the one hand, and secular-minded liberals and Islamists on the other. The second level of conflict is between the Center and periphery and is rooted in a long history of unequal distribution of power and wealth along regional, ethnic, and racial lines. This

level is characterized by armed conflicts, including those in Darfur, South Kordofan, and Eastern Sudan. Efforts to consolidate power through the instrumentalization of ethnicity and religion by successive governments, dominated by Arab elites at the Center, characterize the main drivers of conflict in Sudan. In fact, there is wide consensus in the scholarly literature on Sudan that the country’s central political problem is its political elite, and their decision-making and behavior with respect to pivotal national political and economic questions (Khalid 1990; de Waal 2017). Scholars have correctly noted that the challenges facing Sudan are a result of the failure of previous regimes to establish legitimate bureaucratic and economic institutions to resolve the ethnic divisions dating back to the colonial era (Elbattahani 2017). These include a disintegrated state, ongoing conflicts, fragile state institutions, and continuing economic crisis.

A recent report (Mustafa 2022) noted that the ousted Transitional Government inherited a weak economy characterized by widespread corruption and state capture. On the war’s eve, economic activity in Sudan was concentrated in a small number of mostly government companies and, most significantly, upwards of 70% of public sector wages (amounting to 35% of the 2020 budget) went towards the various security and military apparatuses created by the deposed regime (Mustafa 2022, 2). To be sure, at a general level, Sudan’s crisis is the culmination of decades of economic mismanagement in the context of elite political contestation and competition. However, the root causes and evolving dynamics of the war are due to what can be usefully termed a deeply “bifurcated” economy with profound political consequences. More specifically, successive authoritarian regimes utilized the formal as well as the

informal and *illicit* economy as key components to build loyal coalitions in civil society through a system of patron-clientelism: a process which, in the context of shifting domestic and regional economic dynamics, would set the prelude, first to revolution, and then war.

The End of the Oil Boom and the Unraveling of an Authoritarian State

Ultimately, it was the end of the oil boom era which served as a critical juncture in Sudan's history directly resulting in the unraveling of Omar al-Bashir's authoritarian regime. The decline in oil revenue resulting from the 2011 secession of South Sudan led to a deepening of the economic crisis in the country and eroded the state's control over the economy. This, in turn, weakened the former regime's patronage networks, strengthened rivalries among the ruling and militant Islamist National Congress Party's (NCP) leadership, and exacerbated social and economic grievances across a wide spectrum of Sudanese in both urban and rural areas, laying the groundwork for the 2018-2019 popular uprising. Before Sudan's partition in 2011, the formal economy was buttressed by oil which accounted for 50% of domestic revenue and 95% of export earnings. Following the South's secession, Sudan lost 75% of its oil export revenue, resulting in a major deterioration of its fiscal situation (Ministry of Welfare and Social Security, 1-2). It also aggravated the already stark imbalance between center and periphery in social and economic development. According to the Bashir regime's own Ministry of Welfare and Social Security (MWSS) at the time, the loss of oil resulted in cuts to development and federal transfers to the states by 26% and 20%, respectively. It also resulted in the depreciation of the Sudanese pound against the

US dollar, producing a dramatic spike in the average inflation rate, which rose to 42% in the summer of 2011, up from an average of 13% in 2010 (MWSS, 1-2). Moreover, since most food commodities are imported, the rise in inflation worsened poverty levels and impoverished many in the middle class.

It is for these largely structural reasons that the coalition behind the 2018 uprising came to be organized around a wide range of social groups across all regions in the country. The stark decline of oil revenue changed the social and economic landscape and triggered protests largely because the economy had been growing, rather than declining, at a dramatic rate prior to South Sudan's secession. Between 2000 and 2009, real growth in the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) averaged 8%. More importantly, in terms of the population's livelihood, per capita income increased from \$776 US in 2004 to \$1,570 US in 2009 (MWSS, 1-2).

But these economic developments also had profound political consequences for state formation and decline. More specifically, the boom period enabled the Islamist-dominated ruling National Congress Party (NCP) to expand its patronage networks in rural and urban areas. In what was a boon period in the building of an Islamist "deep" state, the regime embarked on the creation of state governments across the country and funded thousands of local government bureaucrats. During this period, "Sudan's political economy consolidated around a rentier crony capitalist system, reliant on oil revenues. At the center, it functioned as a centralized kleptocracy and in the far peripheries of southern Sudan, Darfur, South Kordofan, and the Blue Nile (de Waal 2019). Indeed, although the formal economy was expanding, the benefits were unequally distributed. The allocation

of services, employment, and infrastructural projects remained concentrated in Khartoum state and reflected a distinct political logic designed to appease urban constituencies. During most of the 2010s, approximately 60% of development spending was on five major projects located within the central triangle in the North (World Bank 2007, 14). Moreover, while foreign investment expanded during this period it was primarily directed to the oil sector, construction, and services. By contrast, agricultural and other traditional exports were neglected, exacerbating inequality across regional and ethnic cleavages. The legacy of these developments is that they worsened rural poverty and unemployment since upwards of 50% of the rural labor force is engaged in agricultural activities. As of 2009 (a decade before the uprising), the incidence of poverty among the urban and rural populations stood at 26% and 57.6%, respectively. Moreover, figures in this period indicate that poverty levels were far higher in Darfur and the East in comparison with Khartoum and the central states (Ministry of Social Affairs and Security 2012, 13). This deepening inequality across regions and between center and periphery explains the deep-seated grievances in regions such as Darfur and Eastern Sudan and the regional and ethnic nature of the violence associated with the ongoing war.

The Illicit Economy and the Politics of Militancy

If the erosion of the formal economy set the stage for popular mobilization and protest, two sectors of the *informal economy* more directly point to the political dynamics that served as drivers of the war, albeit to different degrees: the parallel market in foreign currency monopolized by militants and the emergence of gold as a key component of the political economy and a principal source

of finance for the RSF (Benson and Makawi 2021). Importantly, the long history of political manipulation of both the informal and formal economy by the Islamists determined the balance of military-civilian relations in favor of the Islamist-dominated SAF. Gaafar Nimeiri (1969-1985) was the first to set the institutional and political foundation of Sudan's present "deep state," linking the domestic economy to military and security interests. However, it was the military authoritarian strategy of *tamkeen* (or empowerment), ushered in by militant Islamists following the 1989 military coup, that fundamentally shaped the character of both state institutions and power dynamics between Sudan's political elite and civil society forces (Bartlett 2020, 46-69). The policy of *tamkeen* contained three essential pillars that served as drivers of conflict by deepening divisions among Sudanese across class, sect, ethnicity, and region in unprecedented ways (Mann 2014, 561-578). The first pillar focused on establishing political and economic hegemony in favor of the Islamist elite organized around the National Islamic Front (NIF) and later the National Congress Party (NCP). This strategy included selling off state-owned enterprises to the Islamist regime's allies, coercing businessmen to grant shares to NCP loyalists, and awarding tax reductions to regime-friendly businesses (Gallab 2008). In a pattern similar to the present, Islamist leaders began the hoarding and selective distribution of commodities such as wheat, sesame seed, gum arabic, and petrol (Khalid 2003). The value of illicit financial flows from Sudan between 1970 and 2008 alone was an astronomical USD \$16 billion, dwarfing that of the formal economy (Kar and Smith 2010). But if the economic policies of *tamkeen* resulted in the Islamists' monopolization of both the formal and informal economic sectors in Sudan, these policies also institutionalized and expanded the SAF's

role in the economy (Verhoeven 2013, 118-140). The creation of the Military Industrial Corporation (MIC) in the early 1990s was a key component that further built the edifice of the “deep state. The MIC granted the SAF practical control over a dozen companies that produced military hardware. SAF’s economic activities later grew beyond the MIC to include a range of civilian industries and sectors (Bartlett 2020, 56; Gallab 2008). The second pillar of *tamkeen* centered on purging the Islamists’ rivals in civil society. Upon assuming power, the Islamist regime, now effectively headed by President Abdel-Fatih Burhan, dismissed thousands of members of the military and the bureaucracy, and banned or coopted labor and trade unions as well as professional associations, gravely weakening civil society actors (Bartlett 202, 51-57). The third pillar, and the one most significant in understanding the nature of the war, was the establishment of militias operating in parallel to the National Army. Under Bashir, the regime utilized these irregular forces to wage a brutal counter-insurgency war against rebels in Darfur while simultaneously deploying them to suppress pro-democracy uprisings in urban areas, including in the capital of Khartoum, throughout the mid to late 2000s. Importantly, this policy was also designed to undermine what was an already weakened national army: an army that historically had been the locus point of a series of coups against incumbent military and civilian regimes throughout Sudan’s post-independence period. Bashir’s regime, having learned from the past, sought to “coup-proof” its rule by eliciting the support from its sponsorship of, and partnership with, a wide range of militias, including, most notably, the *Janjaweed*, which later was transformed into the Rapid Support Forces under the leadership of Mohamed Hamdan Dagalo, known as “Hemed-ti.”

It is against this backdrop that the emergence of the economy as a key arena of political competition and fragmentation following the 2018-19 uprising leading up to the war must be understood. During the transition between 2018 and 2021, two political factions emerged in the Center: the remnants of the NIF’s Islamists coalition linked to members of the NCP who were primarily responsible for building the “deep state” in the 1990s; and a relatively new group (or coalition) composed of SAF leaders as well as the RSF militia now fighting on opposite sides in the war. But whereas in the past the Islamists represented a relatively coherent group, in the transition that followed the revolution, clear fissures emerged between military leaders heading the Transitional Military Council (TMC) and a newly resurgent Islamist ideological group wielding significant control over the security services (Africa Confidential 2020, 1). Tensions between the TMC and the Islamists evolved over time, and this continues as the Islamists continue to exert influence on the Army’s leadership in prosecuting the war and obstructing any reconciliation with either the RSF or civil society groups. These divisions were also evident during the transition. The TMC took control over many large Islamist-owned businesses and curtailed the power of the NISS and even worked towards dismantling several militia forces by confiscating their assets and closing their bank accounts (Africa Confidential 2020, 1). However, even as the TMC and the Islamists competed during the transition, there is significant evidence that both are now working to undermine the pro-democracy movement, prolong the war, and rebuild their political and economic power. One aim of the war is thus to weaken the civilian pro-democracy movement and, in the case of the militant Islamists heading the Army, to *regain* political power and control over the economy and the

state's security apparatus.

Following the October 25, 2021 coup, the TMC, under Burhan, mended relations with the Islamists and NCP, releasing some of the most militant Islamist politicians from prison, reinstating some to the bureaucracy and the state's security apparatus, and generally affording them the opportunity to act as spoilers to any attempt at reconciliation with civilian forces or efforts at mediation sponsored by the international community. Indeed, Burhan continues to be focused on the same objectives he pursued during the now aborted transition, including preserving the SAF's influence over Sudanese civil society and politics; protecting its vast business empire, some of which is now organized as the Defense Industries System (DIS) that replaced the MIC in 2022, but also includes control over business conglomerates involved in construction, mining, pharmaceuticals, and livestock (Africa Confidential 2020); and protecting its formal budget allocation, which makes up a substantial portion of the national budget. A key reason explaining Burhan and the Islamists' motivations in the present war is their opposition to any attempts at dismantling the institutions of the "deep state," which was a key demand of civilian forces during the period of the 2018-19 Revolution. Even as Burhan eliminated the committee to dismantle the assets of the previous regime immediately after the 2021 coup, the leadership of the SAF has continued to insist that all SAF companies are "subject to public reviews, taxes and customs law," arguing that political parties are the ones rejecting regulations [and] accusing civilian politicians, and not the Islamists, of "working to acquire goods, property, and assets of SAF companies and investments for themselves" (Radio Dabanga 2020).

Sudan's economic crisis leading up to the present war can be attributed, to a degree, to SAF companies and investments and the long history of the SAF and the Islamists' manipulation of the informal economy. The threat to these interests is one reason for the October 2021 coup and also the reason militants in the Army have subsequently stalled peace negotiations (Abdelazziz and Eltahir, 2021). However, understanding this crisis requires an analysis of the *mechanisms* utilized to distort and control the domestic economy. Indeed, any deep assessment of the conflict must not only address the nature of the economy but also the mechanisms utilized by the military and Islamist elite to distort, manipulate, and preserve control over the "deep state" at all costs. The SAF collects significant "off the books" funding from its businesses, which increases SAF's independence and undermines other civilian-owned interests, as well as civilian politicians, by depriving them of significant tax revenue. This is because SAF-owned companies continue to benefit from NCP-era policies that exempt them from paying taxes (Bartlett 2020, 48). Furthermore, by operating outside of Sudan's Central Bank, the SAF's involvement in key export sectors like mining, cotton, and gum arabic distorts the balance of trade in these markets. It allows the SAF to directly acquire foreign currency, which enables it to influence Sudan's currency black market in ways that finance its military operations and the security apparatus more generally. This is part of a broader strategy of consolidating control over the economy and depriving non-Islamists access to revenue. Under the NCP regime, the National Intelligence and Security Service (NISS)—which was controlled by the regime's Islamists—also had a large stake in the "deep state" (Musso 2017, 112-128). Consequently, whereas the desire to protect its economic interests is what led to deep fissures

and contestation between Burhan and the civilians in Sudan; intense competition also subsequently emerged between the SAF and Islamist remnants of the previous regime and the para-military militia headed by Mohamed Hamdan Dagolo, whose revenue is generated from the illicit arms and gold trade rather than from the Islamist' "deep states" coffers.

Recruiting Militias: “Conflict” Gold

If the leadership of the Sudanese Army and their Islamist supporters have long relied on the monopolization of state institutions to bolster their economic wealth and political power, another segment of the economy has financed the now-powerful RSF militia, the rival protagonist in Sudan's ongoing war. By the mid-2010s, it was gold rather than oil that came to heavily influence the trajectory of Sudan's political economy. Following the loss of a large proportion of oil revenue in 2011, Omar Bashir turned to gold to bolster his weakened patronage networks. Between 2012 and 2017, gold production increased by an astronomical 141 percent, and by 2018, only a year before the uprising, the country emerged as the world's twelfth largest gold producer (Elbadawi and Suliman 2018). Importantly, benefits accruing from this new gold “boom” are distributed in a far more decentralized fashion than those from oil exports. This is because most gold exports are smuggled illegally, and thus the bulk of the value of gold escapes state coffers. In 2016, one study found this gap equaled US\$4.1 billion, noting that while the Central Bank of Sudan reported gold exports of US\$8.6 billion, its trading partners reported gold imports of US\$12.7 billion (Elbadawi and Suliman 2018). This suggests that the value gap, equaling an enormous 47.7 percent of Sudan's reported gold exports, ends up in private hands.

This not only represented a huge financial loss for the Sudanese government, there is also clear evidence that much of this revenue is captured by members of the military and security establishment, and especially the RSF, which has utilized this lucrative trade as a central recruiting tool to employ fighters against the army, not only in Darfur but throughout the country including in the central state of Gezira and the capital of Khartoum.

Importantly, the transition from oil to gold has shifted the country's political economy from a more centralized oil-based patronage system towards a more fractured system whereby rents, derived from gold smuggling, are utilized to fund the recruitment of irregular militia forces has come to play a central role. It is for this reason that analysts have described Sudan's political economy as increasingly decentralized and characterized by a “shadow economy”; a situation where a multitude of interests and actors now vie for resources, rents, and markets, characterizing the nature of state failure and the country's armed conflict. The gold mining sector is an important illustrative case of this decentralized but nevertheless coherently organized sector with important political consequences for the present war. This sector can essentially be divided along three dimensions: artisanal mining, small-scale mining, and large-scale production (United Nations Trade and Development-UNCTAD 2016). The most significant of these is the artisanal sector, which consists of unprocessed mining, known locally as “gharabeel.” It is dominated by the Rashaida tribe in Kassala State on the borders of Eritrea along the Red Sea, but this type of production also spans the Blue Nile, River state, Northern State, Kassala, and South Kordofan states. This sector accounts for approximately 85% of total production and

is responsible for 90% of all gold smuggled outside of the country. It can be characterized as informal because it is unlicensed by the government and does not contribute to government tax revenue. In other words, it largely evades the government's efforts to redirect profits from this sector to the central bank, and its mode of operation and decentralized nature underpins the unraveling of the state from Sudanese society in ways that now threaten to lead to the de facto, if not de jure, division of the country.

Conflict or Cooperation: The Role of External Actors

While the primary dynamics driving conflict in Sudan are internal, regional actors and other players further afield play influential roles. Sudan's current crisis must be understood within the broader configuration of relations in its region. This includes the Gulf, the Horn of Africa, and particularly the Red Sea, and reflects intense rivalries and competing interests among Middle Eastern states and the countries in the Horn of Africa, and particularly Ethiopia. Over the last two decades, Saudi Arabia, the UAE, and to a lesser extent Qatar and Turkey, all have increased their engagement in the Red Sea (United Institute of Peace 2020, 1-60). The Gulf states have economic as well as strategic interests vis-à-vis Sudan. Sudan has long been perceived as a potential "breadbasket" by Gulf states with great potential for investment in land and agriculture. They also clearly consider the Horn of Africa critical in their struggle against Iran, which they perceive as an "existential threat" (United Institute of Peace 2020). Saudi Arabia and the UAE have long worried about Iranian encirclement through the Straits of Hormuz and Bab el-Mandeb (Medani 2012, 12-30). These concerns were further heightened by Iranian

support for the Houthi movement in Yemen, which led to military intervention by a Saudi-led coalition in 2015.

The Gulf states also have economic interests in the Red Sea. Both the Emirates and Saudi Arabia have developed ports and established military bases in the region. The UAE has a base in Eritrea (Assab), while Saudi Arabia has signed an agreement for a base in Djibouti. Ideological issues are also significant with respect to the Gulf's relationship with Sudan. Saudi Arabia, the UAE, and Egypt continue to be wary of an Islamist coalition heading the Sudanese government. All three would like to limit the Muslim Brotherhood's influence in the region, while Qatar and Turkey are more supportive of Islamism. The Egyptian-Sudanese relationship cooled after the 2013 military coup against President Morsi because Cairo accused the ousted Bashir regime of providing a haven and even training Brotherhood members escaping Egypt (United States Institute of Peace 2020, 1-60).

An even more important issue for Egypt concerns tensions over the Nile River. In 2020, Ethiopia started filling the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD), a US\$ 4.8 billion hydroelectric dam on the Blue Nile. This has transformed relations between Egypt and its upstream neighbors (United States Institute of Peace 2020, 27). Officials in Addis Ababa argue the GERD will have no major impact on water flow to both Sudan and Egypt. They argue instead that the Dam will not only provide affordable electric power to Ethiopia (and potentially other states); it would also provide the necessary water sources so crucial to managing the problem of recurring droughts in the region. Egypt, on the other hand, insists that the GERD will reduce its supply of water and continues to try to secure a political agreement over the timetable for

filling the GERD's reservoir in a way that would minimize the adverse effects to its own population and development plans (United States Institute of Peace 2020, 27).

For its part, even as the war continues, the de facto government headed by Burhan is caught between competing Egyptian and Ethiopian interests. From Sudan's perspective, the GERD would enable the country to use more water from its own allocation, instead of allowing this water to flow downstream to Egypt. It would also end the seasonal fluctuations of the Blue Nile and allow for the expansion of agriculture, thereby permitting two or three crop rotations every year instead of one. Yet, fear lingers that the GERD could threaten the safety of Sudan's own dams and make it more difficult for the government to manage its own development projects. Prior to the war, both Egypt and Ethiopia had tried to sway Sudan towards their respective positions, which, according to reports, had deepened factionalism within Khartoum's transitional government (Mbaku 2020). For its part, the United States continues to voice support for an end to the war and a peaceful transition to democracy in Sudan. Moreover, while Egypt, the UAE, and Saudi Arabia were quick to support Abdel-Fatih al-Burhan following his coup in 2021, Saudi Arabia has now partnered with the U.S. in the latter's efforts to broker an agreement that is calling for a cease-fire and a transition to a civilian-led government. More recently, on September 12, 2025, the US sponsored talks over Sudan, bringing together the most important external actors to the war: Saudi Arabia, Egypt, and the UAE. While this is an encouraging sign, there is clear evidence that competing interests remain. Egypt and Saudi Arabia continue to support Sudan's military ostensibly to safeguard their strategic interest in the region as well as to forestall a democratic tide

in the country, and simultaneously weaken the influence of the Muslim Brotherhood. It remains unclear whether the US, the Gulf states, and Egypt will be able to bridge the violent rivalry between Burhan and Hemedti. Hemedti enjoys close relations with Abu Dhabi, based on their economic relations and cooperation during the Yemen war, and has a wide network of fighters in Libya and Chad. The war has clearly shown that Hemedti has personal ambitions that pit him against Burhan and the SAF.

War, the “Deep State”, and the threat of democracy

Ultimately, however, what undermined the transition to democracy was the previous government's inability to dismantle the vestiges of the vast financial empire wielded by the security sector and the military. Indeed, prior to the war several analysts noted that the biggest risk to Sudan lay in the financial power of the military heading the transitional government at the time. As noted above, the military and the security apparatus control companies involved in oil, gum arabic, sesame, weapons, fuel, wheat, telecommunications, banking, real estate, and gold. The military's defense companies produce a vast array of consumer goods and retain a large share of the country's banking institutions. Moreover, if the military controls large sectors of the economy, the RSF also benefits from subsidies, which allow it and the SAF to hoard commodities and profit from their sale in the black market at inflated prices to consumers. While accurate data is difficult to obtain, there is some evidence to suggest that the Military controls companies such as al-Fakher, as-Sobat, and SIN, which dominate the market in fuel and wheat. According to one report, the SAF controls 60% of the market in wheat, although Sudanese sources have

noted that former NCP businessmen continue to wield the greatest influence in these markets (Resnick 2021).

These rents - generated from military-state predation - are used by Burhan to dole out patronage to Islamist-allied forces in the Army. These are the same loyal clients Omar Bashir patronized and supported prior to his ouster in 2019 (Medani 2022). Nevertheless, while a focus on the military and security apparatus' power over civil society is warranted, what is missing in analysis of Sudan's "deep state" is an examination of the political and economic factors that have worked to sustain the patronage system in the first place; a system forged under Bashir and now exploited by Burhan and Hemedti, albeit for different political objectives.

Consequently, at the root of the tragic war is the legacy of an illegitimate and authoritarian central authority and weak political institutions. Gold smuggling, discussed in detail above, is an illustrative example of both the challenges of Sudan's "deep state" as well as the prospects for strengthening institutions in ways that promote good governance. Indeed, if the combination of weak regulatory and legal institutions has fueled the informal and illicit smuggling of the nation's gold resources and provided financing for militia-led violence and war, they have also posed a direct challenge to a transition to civilian rule or negotiated peace. This is primarily because the trade has benefited the interests of the military and security forces rather than Sudanese civil society. Since Bashir's overthrow in April 2019, along with the head of the army, Abdul Fattah al-Burhan, it is Mohamed Hemedti Hamdan Dagolo, the RSF leader, who has wielded disproportionate control over the country's now failed transition. Like Burhan and his allies, Hemedti and his militia saw

the potential of Sudanese democracy as a grave threat to their political power and vast wealth. It is for these reasons that both are standing in the way of international efforts at mitigating conflict, negotiating a cease-fire, and building a sustainable peace.

War Making as State Making: The Struggle for Sudan

While in the first two years of the war in Sudan the conflict primarily represented a rivalry between a para-legal militia and the Sudan Armed Forces, in its current manifestation it is best described as a violent contest between two forms of state-building efforts. In the summer of 2025, the RSF announced the establishment of a parallel government based in the city of Nyala in South Darfur to rival the de facto government led by General Burhan in the eastern city of Port-Sudan on the Red Sea. Consequently, Sudan now represents two de facto political entities, each seeking to build new states from scratch: one that seeks to build a state on the edifice of the former Islamist authoritarian state; the other, seeking to form, through brutal violence against civilians, a governance structure ostensibly built on a secular and non-racial government of "unity and peace." Both have already enacted citizenship measures and announced a new currency designed to restrict the right to citizenship to only those Sudanese in areas under their respective control, while simultaneously demarcating new economic borders in their nascent efforts at state-building.

Sudan's evolving political economy and particularly the erosion of the state's formal extractive capacity, combined with the absence of an autonomous and legitimate national standing army, are two principal factors that have resulted in the worst humanitarian crisis in the world. These two issues will continue

to determine the relative success of the ongoing state-building efforts. This, in turn, will determine whether Sudan will retain its territorial integrity or splinter as occurred with South Sudan in 2011.

The evidence suggests that, absent a resolution to the war, it is unlikely there will be a formal separation. The RSF does not have the legitimacy among the population it controls and, importantly, it does not have the mechanisms of revenue generation that would culminate in state consolidation (Tilly 1985). For its part, the SAF, is similarly burdened by a lack of legitimacy because of the authoritarian policies of the Islamist regime. Perhaps more importantly, the SAF is riven with divisions between Islamist stalwarts and the rank-and-file officers are divided along ethnic lines. Equally important is that while the Army has strong support from regional powers more interested in a reliable military alliance than the democratic aspirations of the Sudanese population, they are nevertheless cautious about the influence and power Islamists still wield among the upper echelons of the SAF leadership.

Understanding the current dynamics of war as a contest between two rival military and political actors waging war and extracting revenue, albeit through violent means, in order to build new states also helps to explain the logic and severity of the mass-scale violence against civilians. For its part, the RSF has used windfall profits from the gold trade and its strategic alliance with the UAE to expand its recruitment drives and to wage war against the civilian population, even as it battles its former partners among the SAF leadership. At the time of writing, the RSF controls most of the provinces of Darfur and has waged a brutal siege of the northern Darfur capital of al Fasher. There is clear evidence

that, as with most insurgent militias (Jentzsch 2015; Weinstein 2006), RSF forces are motivated by material and strategic objectives rather than ideology. However, this is not the case with its rival and the architect of Sudan's war. Over the course of the war, the more militant remnants of the Islamist National Congress Party have managed to wield disproportionate influence over the upper echelons of the military establishment and especially the high-ranking officers that make up the powerful Security and Intelligence Committee. These stalwarts of the Islamist movement are intent on pursuing the war with the view that anything short of a military victory would usher in an era of civilian or militia-led rule that would ultimately oust them from authority and state power. It is for this reason, that following the October 2021 coup, General Burhan released some prominent Islamist militants from prison, appointed them to high political office, and has generally allowed them to act as spoilers in attempts at reconciliation with civilian forces or efforts at mediation sponsored by the US and Saudi Arabia – and more recently, the Quad, made up of the US, Saudi Arabia, Egypt and the UAE. Moreover, as students of insurgent politics have long observed, in contexts where nascent state builders and their allied militias are unable to provide protection, administer justice, and collect taxes to fund social programs generating legitimacy for their cause, they frequently resort to severe forms of mass violence against civilians so as to “punish their enemies and sanction behavior through extreme forms of violence,” sometimes going as far as to utilize food and sexual violence as weapons of war (Stanton 2015; Kalyvas 2006).

Conclusion

If the roots of the war in Sudan are rooted in decades of authoritarian rule and the mili-

tarization of politics, an important obstacle to a cessation of hostilities and long term political stability has to do with the country's strategic and financial dependence on regional actors. The prospect of successful state building, wherein domestic sources of revenue are captured and allocated in the service of consolidating politico-military rule and providing a modicum of public goods to the population, are in this instance undermined by the exigencies of regional constraints and interventions. Both the RSF and the SAF are greatly dependent on external rather than local revenue sources, whether to fund their war campaigns or build durable and legitimate institutions in their respective territories. Taken together, these factors preclude the generation of domestic or international legitimacy that is so crucial to achieving peace and stability for Sudan. What is at stake for the region is also consequential. Bordering seven countries, the Sahel region, and the contested Red Sea, the continuation of the Sudanese war threatens the long-term strategic and economic interests of several countries in the region. It threatens Egypt's interests over the Nile waters and its contested southern frontier; Turkey and Saudi Arabia's ambitions over the Red Sea region; Iran's efforts to influence developments in the region through its military support of Burhan; and UAE's long-term vision for their investments in Sudan and Africa.

Consequently, for students of the political science of the Middle East and North Africa, Sudan is an important case for the study of a variety of themes central to the politics of region. It allows for the examination of the role of authoritarian legacies and the roots of war; an understanding of the precarious balance between military-civil relations that can result in popular revolution, as well as fatal reversals resulting in deep seated conflicts

as in Syria; the logic and patterns of violence associated with divided and rival efforts at state building as in Libya and Somalia; the dynamics underpinning the transformation of para-legal militias into an autonomous force waging war against its former partners at the level of the state; and the relationship between Islamist political ideology and rule in countries in the region divided along ethnic, racial and sectarian cleavages. ♦

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